

Coordination Complexes of Dibenzyltin(IV) Salts with N_2S_2 Donor Ligands and their Reactions

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Some complexes of dibenzyltin(IV) salts with two N_2S_2 donor ligands have been prepared and a number of reactions, viz. addition, replacement and cyclisation reactions were performed and studied. The complexes and their derivatives have been characterised and found to possess octahedral geometry on the basis of physicochemical studies.

Numerous organometallic complexes involving Schiff bases and macrocycles have been reported from this laboratory¹. However, very little work has been done on the reactivity of these complexes. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of dibenzyltin(IV) complexes with some N_2S_2 ligands derived from the condensation of *o*-aminobenzenethiol and dichloroethane/glyoxal. The complexes have also been subjected to addition, replacement and cyclisation reactions in order to study the effect of these reactions on the stability of the metal-carbon bond present in the skeleton of the compounds.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes formed by the reaction of $Bz_2SnCl_2/Bz_2Sn(ClO_4)_2$ (where Bz = benzyl) and the ligands are high melting crystalline solids. Their elemental analysis are in agreement with 1 : 2 stoichiometry and the molar conductance values in DMF ($130-170 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) correspond to 1 : 2 electrolytes indicating the general formulae for the complexes as $[Bz_2Sn(L_1 \text{ or } L_2)]X_2$, where L_1 = bis(2-benzenethiol)ethylenediamine, L_2 = di(2-aminophenyl)ethanebisulphide and $X = Cl^-$ or ClO_4^- .

The ir spectra of ligand L_1 and L_2 show weak bands at $3200 cm^{-1}$ due to CH stretching

and three sharp bands at 1600, 1580 and $1465 cm^{-1}$ due to aromatic ring vibrations. The bands at 1515 and $750 cm^{-1}$ correspond to C-S stretching^{2,3} and that at $1300 cm^{-1}$ may be assigned to C-N stretching vibration. The ligand L_1 also shows a strong band at $1610 cm^{-1}$ due to C=N stretching and a medium intensity band at $2515 cm^{-1}$ corresponding to SH stretching vibration⁴. On the otherhand, ligand L_2 shows a band at $3465 cm^{-1}$ due to NH vibration and the absence of band at $2515 cm^{-1}$ due to SH stretching confirms the formation of the ligand as a result of condensation of thiol groups with dichloroethane.

The ir spectra of all the complexes show a small positive shift in the bands due to aromatic ring vibrations indicating the coordination through the groups attached to the aromatic rings. In the ir spectra of complexes 1 and 2, the azomethine, SH, C-S and NH stretching vibrations show small negative shifts and appear respectively at 1605, 2510, 1015 and $745 cm^{-1}$. This clearly indicates the coordination of nitrogen and sulphur atoms of the ligands to the central tin atom³.

The ir spectra of the macrocyclic complexes obtained from ligand L_1 and L_2 show the absence of band at $2515 (SH)$ and $3400 cm^{-1} (NH)$ indicating the formation of macrocyclic complexes as a result of template condensation of the complexes

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS.

Compd. no. *	M.p. (°C)	Yield %	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)				Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			C	H	N	Sn	
L ₁	143	87	61.55 (61.76)	4.22 (4.41)	9.89 (10.29)	—	—
L ₂	72	82	60.16 (60.86)	5.21 (5.79)	10.51 (10.14)	—	—
1a	75	64	51.94 (52.17)	3.87 (4.03)	4.02 (4.34)	18.02 (18.47)	160.08
1b	—	68	—	—	3.51 (3.62)	15.28 (15.41)	161.54
2a	180	61	51.59 (51.85)	4.51 (4.62)	4.18 (4.32)	18.22 (18.36)	158.16
2b	—	58	—	—	3.44 (3.60)	15.18 (15.33)	153.75
3a	240	67	53.59 (53.73)	4.02 (4.18)	4.03 (4.18)	17.61 (17.76)	148.72
3b	—	62	—	—	3.42 (3.51)	14.79 (14.91)	144.08
4a	170d	54	52.77 (52.94)	5.02 (5.14)	6.66 (6.86)	14.33 (14.58)	153.12
4b	—	58	—	—	5.84 (5.93)	12.46 (12.60)	147.78
5a	240	47	56.68 (56.85)	4.27 (4.48)	3.52 (3.49)	14.74 (14.83)	138.79
5b	—	49	—	—	2.89 (3.01)	12.62 (12.79)	133.65
6a	240	43	56.78 (57.00)	4.12 (4.25)	6.81 (7.00)	14.58 (14.87)	159.76
6b	—	47	—	—	— (3.02)	12.64 (12.82)	160.24
7a	200d	52	51.51 (51.69)	4.14 (4.39)	—	17.98 (18.30)	156.89
7b	—	55	—	—	—	15.02 (15.29)	157.77
8a	240	51	60.98 (61.16)	4.42 (4.61)	3.14 (3.39)	14.22 (14.44)	140.72
8b	—	48	—	—	2.81 (2.94)	12.36 (12.50)	146.22
9a	210d	43	52.18 (52.45)	4.38 (4.64)	3.68 (3.82)	16.02 (16.25)	133.15
9b	—	47	—	—	3.01 (3.25)	13.68 (13.83)	138.67
10a	240	45	47.78 (47.94)	3.81 (3.99)	3.24 (3.49)	14.71 (14.85)	158.15
10b	—	54	—	—	2.89 (3.01)	12.68 (12.80)	148.97

*a = chloride derivative, b = perchlorate derivative.

of L₁ and L₂ with dichloroethane and glyoxal respectively.

The complexes **4**, **5** and **6** are obtained by the ligand replacement reactions in which morpholine, pyridine and ethylenediamine behave as secondary ligands and are found to replace the SH groups from the coordination sites. In the ir spectra of complexes **4**, **5** and **6**, the bands due to C-S at 1015 and 750 cm⁻¹ remain unaltered showing that the thiol groups of the ligand do not participate in the coordination and in their place the secondary ligand is coordinated to tin atom. This is confirmed by the analytical data and ir spectra of these complexes which show shifting of the concerned bands⁶.

The complexes **7**, **8**, **9** and **10** are obtained as a result of the reactions of amino groups of the ligands. Some additional bands are observed in the ir spectra in addition to the usual bands in the range 3 100–3 500 (OH), ~ 1 700 (C=O), ~ 500 (C=Cl) and ~ 1 300 (C-N) cm⁻¹ for these complexes.

In the ir spectra of all the complexes two bands of medium intensity at 510 ± 5 and 530 ± 5 cm⁻¹ are attributed to Sn-CH₂- symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations respectively⁹. Two more weak intensity bands are observed at 425 ± 5 and 370 ± 5 cm⁻¹ (which are absent in the spectra of the free ligands) are attributed to ν_{Sn←N} vibration¹⁰. The former set of bands clearly indicates the existence of linear C-Sn-C species with benzyl groups in *trans*-axial positions. The presence of ionic chloride is confirmed by a medium intensity band¹¹ at 570 ± 5 cm⁻¹ and that of ionic perchlorate by bands¹² at 630 ± 5 and 1 050 ± 4 cm⁻¹.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of the ligands, one doublet at δ 6.20 (4H) and two triplets at δ 6.60 (2H) and 7.30 (4H) are observed due to the phenyl protons. In addition, ligand L₁ shows singlets at δ 5.50 (2H) and 2.25 (2H) to SH and CH protons respectively.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of all the complexes,

signals due to aromatic protons merge together and are seen as a broad multiplet at δ 8.40–6.50. A singlet at δ 1.85 (4H) is observed in the complexes which is assigned to the CH₂ protons of dibenzyl groups attached to tin atom.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of complexes **1** and **2** almost all the signals show a downfield shift in their positions. This clearly indicates the coordination through nitrogen and sulphur atoms. The formation of the macrocyclic complexes is evidenced by the presence of two singlets due to CH and CH₂ protons at δ 2.50 (2H) and 2.05 (4H) respectively, and the absence of singlets due to SH or NH protons. In the ¹H nmr spectra of complexes **8** an additional singlet at δ 6.00 (2H) is observed which is attributed to OH protons. The spectra of complexes **8**, **9** and **10** which possess the same skeleton structure as **2** show additional singlets at δ 3.20 (2H, CH), 1.75 (4H, CH₂) and 1.35 (6H, CH₃).

Based on the above discussion it is concluded that complexes **1**, **2** and **3** possess octahedral structures in which the ligand is coordinated through the nitrogen and sulphur atoms whereas the axial positions are occupied by the benzyl groups. In complexes **4**, **5** and **6**, the sulphur atoms are not coordinated and instead two moles of pyridine/morpholine or one mole of ethylene-diamine are coordinated to give an octahedral structure. It is also observed that in all the reactions of complexes **1** and **2** the metal-carbon bond remains intact and no net structural change occurs in the resulting complexes.

Experimental

Dibenzyltin dichloride was prepared by reported method⁹ and all other chemicals were of A.R. grade. The solvents were distilled and dried before use by standard methods. Molar conductance of the complexes (10⁻³ M solution in DMF) was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Tin was estimated by standard method¹³. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically on a Varlo-Erba 1108 instrument, and ir and ¹H nmr spectra

were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer and Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer respectively at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Di(2-benzenethiol)ethylenediamine(L₁): 2-Aminothiophenol (2.5 g, 0.02 mol) in dry methanol (20 ml) was added dropwise to dry methanolic solution (10 ml) of glyoxal (0.58 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 8–10 h on a water-bath and filtered. Upon concentration of the filtrate the crude product obtained was recrystallised from methanol and washed with diethyl ether.

Di(2-aminophenyl)ethanebisulphide(L₂): A mixture of 2-aminothiophenol (2.5 g, 0.02 mol) in dry methanol (20 ml) and dichloroethane (1.0 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (10 ml), was refluxed for 7–8 h and then filtered. Filtrate on concentration gave crude product which was recrystallised from absolute ethanol and washed with diethyl ether.

Di(2-benzenethiol)ethylenediaminedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (1): Anhydrous methanolic solution (5 ml) containing Bz₂SnCl₂/Bz₂Sn(ClO₄)₂ (3.72/5.0 g, 0.01 mol) was added gradually to a methanolic solution (10 ml) of L₁ (2.7 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h and then filtered. Upon concentration, the crude product was precipitated out on addition of diethyl ether, which was recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

Di(2-aminothiophenol)ethanebisulphidedibenzyltin-dichloridediperchlorate (2): To a methanolic solution (5 ml) of Bz₂SnCl₂/Bz₂Sn(ClO₄)₂ (3.7/5.0 g, 0.01 mol), a methanolic solution (10 ml) of L₂ (2.7 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring and then refluxed for 8 h. The solution was filtered and upon concentration the resulting crude product was recrystallised from ethanol and washed with diethyl ether.

Dibenzo(e,k)-1,4-diaza-7,10-dithiacyclododeca-2,3-dienedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate(3): The macrocyclic complexes were prepared from both the complexes 1 and 2. To a methanolic solution

(10 ml) of complexes 1 or 2 (0.001 mol), a methanolic solution of dichloroethane (0.1 g, 0.001 mol) or glyoxal (0.06 g, 0.001 mol) was added respectively, and then refluxed for 10–12 h. The solution was then filtered and concentrated to give a crude product which was recrystallised from absolute ethanol and washed with diethyl ether.

Di(2-benzenethiol)ethylenediamine-dimorpholine/dipyridine/ethylenediamine-dibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (4–6): To a solution of 1 (0.001 mol) in dry acetone (20 ml), morpholine/pyridine (0.002 mol)/ethylenediamine (0.001 mol) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–6 h. The solution was then distilled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°).

Di(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanebisulphidedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (7): Complex 2 (0.001 mol) was suspended in dilute HCl (5 N; 3.0 ml) and cooled to 0–5° in an ice-bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.65 g in 10 ml) was added to the above suspension. The cold diazotised solution was added dropwise to dilute H₂SO₄ (2 ml; 1 : 10 solution) maintaining the temperature at 55–60° and the reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h. The solution was then extracted with chloroform and dried over P₄O₁₀ under reduced pressure. The crude product obtained after concentration of chloroform extract was recrystallised from diethyl ether and acetone mixture.

Di(2-benzilidinediphenyl)ethanebisulphidedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (8): To a solution of 2 (0.001 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml), benzaldehyde (0.002 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 7 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the crude product was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°).

Di(2-chloroacetamidophenyl)ethanebisulphidedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (9): To a solution of 2 (0.001 mol) in dry methanol (20 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.002 mol) containing a few drops of dilute acetic acid was added dropwise maintaining

the temperature at 40–45°. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 6 h and filtered. The crude product so obtained was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°).

Di(2-acetamidophenyl)ethanebisulphidedibenzyltin-dichloride/diperchlorate (10) : To a solution of **2** (0.001 mol) in dry methanol (25 ml), acetic anhydride (0.002 mol) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the resulting crude product was recrystallised from petroleum ether.

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